

Frequency Dependent Charge Pumping – A Defect Depth Profiling Tool?

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Abstract— We investigate the validity of using frequency-dependent charge pumping (FD-CP) to determine bulk defect depth distributions. Using simple physical arguments we conclude that: (1) the effective tunneling length to a bulk defect can be very different than its actual physical depth, and (2) only a fraction of detrapping charge may contribute to the CP current (I_{CP}) resulting in analysis errors. Thus, the relationship between frequency and defect depth is much more complex than what has been previously reported.

INTRODUCTION

During the search for alternative gate dielectrics, it quickly became apparent that bulk dielectric defects were a major limiting factor towards successful high-k implementation [1]. As such, the need to better understand these defects became extremely important. One methodology that became popular for this purpose is frequency dependent charge pumping (FD-CP) as a tool for profiling bulk defect spatial distributions [2-12]. FD-CP is thought to have a well-defined relationship between charge pumping (CP) frequency and physical defect depth in the gate dielectric. Having access to bulk defect spatial profiles, especially in the case of complex multi-dielectric stacks, is extremely useful for gate stack development.

The basics of FD-CP are conceptually intuitive. The likelihood of a charge carrier tunneling from a supply of substrate charge into a bulk defect depends on, among other things, the energy barrier width and the time allowed for tunneling to occur. Simplistically speaking, bulk defects farther away from the charge supply (deeper in the gate stack) have a lower tunneling probability compared to defects located much closer to the interface. In CP, changing the CP frequency changes the time allowed for tunneling. Thus, by altering the CP frequency, bulk defects located at different physical depths can be accessed. All one needs to obtain the bulk defect depth distribution is the CP frequency to defect depth relationship.

Establishing this relationship has proven to be quite complicated and often results in controversial conclusions [13-14]. For example, a FD-CP debate emerged in the literature regarding the physical location of stress induced defects in dual layer SiO₂/HfO₂ gate stacks. One camp contends that defects are created in both the bulk HfO₂ and SiO₂ interfacial layer [13]. The other camp contends that while pre-existing defects are present in the bulk HfO₂, primary generation occurs in the SiO₂ interfacial layer [14]. The outcome of this debate has serious development implications, especially reliability. In one case, we need to focus our attention on improving both the SiO₂ and HfO₂ reliability. In the other case, our focus would be

completely different; the primary concern being the need to improve the reliability of only the SiO₂ interfacial layer. The initial HfO₂ quality needs improvement, but the reliability is already satisfactory. The outcome of this ongoing debate has a profound impact on how our attention and resources should be allocated.

The purpose of this paper is not to settle the debate, critically evaluate the different and complex analyses proposed in the literature, or proclaim one camp correct or incorrect. Our goal is to show, using simple physical arguments, that FD-CP is not a suitable methodology to extract these bulk defect spatial profiles.

DISCUSSION

CP is typically imagined as a cyclic electron/hole capture process with the measured CP recombination current (I_{CP}) proportional to the number of defects [15] participating. Historically (production quality SiO₂) bulk defects are essentially negligible and CP is a reliable and common interface defect monitor [15]. However, the higher bulk dielectric defect densities commonly found in high-k based gate stacks cannot be so easily ignored.

Typically, bulk defect participation is considered as a two-step interface defect mediated tunneling event, where charge carriers are first captured at interface defects before tunneling to bulk defects [15]. Zhang *et al.* [16] have argued that geometric and energetic constraints severely limit the ability of bulk defects to contribute to I_{CP} via this mechanism. As a result, the CP frequency to depth relationship becomes poorly defined. Regardless, it is still unclear how to account for bulk defect I_{CP} contributions via direct trapping and detrapping without interface state mediation.

In [15], the main argument against interface mediated bulk defect I_{CP} contribution is that interface states are spatially fixed (unlike unbound inversion charge). As a result, only bulk defects within a short distance into the gate stack can be reached by the tunneling front during each CP half cycle. This is schematically illustrated in 3-D in fig. 1. From the interface defect (red star) perspective, the tunneling front is hemispherical. For a tunneling front of 1 nm (blue hemisphere), the hemisphere volume is 2.1 nm³. If the bulk density is 10⁻²⁰ cm⁻³ (blue dots), on average 0.21 defects are intercepted by the tunneling front volume. Bulk defect contribution through this mode is unlikely.

Fig. 1 has another message. The 2 nm tunneling front originating from the interface defect (white hemisphere) has intercepted a single bulk defect. However, as depicted, this bulk defect is not physically lined up with the interface defect. Since it is the tunneling distance that determines the time

constant, the effective tunneling distance can be very different than the actual physical depth of the defect in the dielectric.

Fig. 1: Gate dielectric (drawn 10 nm x 10 nm x 5 nm) with 10^{20} cm^{-3} bulk defect density (blue dots) and one interface defect (red star). The light blue hemisphere represents a 1 nm tunneling front initiated from the interface defect. The bigger (colorless) hemisphere represents a 2 nm tunneling front.

This is schematically illustrated in 2-D in fig. 2. The interface defect (red star), presumed to be some type of P_b or P_b -like center [17], is located precisely at the Si/dielectric interface. In this 2-D drawing, the tunneling front originating from the interface defect is depicted as a semi-circle. In fig. 2a, the bulk defect and interface defect are physically lined up. This means that the effective tunneling distance equals the actual physical depth of the bulk defect away from the interface. However, in fig 2b, the bulk defect is offset and is no longer physically lined up with the interface defect. The effective tunneling distance between interface and bulk defect remains the same as in fig. 2a, but the actual physical depth of the bulk defect away from the interface is dramatically different. In this case, the actual physical depth is some fraction (depending on the location) of the effective tunneling distance. This illustrates how, even when bulk defects do manage to contribute to I_{CP} through an interface defect mediated process, the bulk defect depth information is very convoluted.

Fig. 2: The (a) bulk (blue circle) and interface (red star) defects are physically lined up; the effective tunneling distance equals the actual physical depth. (b) The bulk defect is offset from the interface defect; the effective tunneling distance is quite different than the actual physical depth.

A plane is shown (broken red lines) in fig. 1 to illustrate a 2 nm tunneling front when tunneling occurs directly from inversion layer electrons. Clearly, the probability of bulk defect participation is much higher. Energetically, this mode of participation is direct trapping and detrapping as shown in fig. 3. Electrons fill bulk defects from the inversion layer (trapping) and flow out to the substrate (detrapping) during the accumulation CP half cycle.

Fig. 3: Schematic illustration of the direct trapping/detrapping mode. (a) Direct capture of charge from the inversion layer and (b) trapped charge emission into the substrate as minority carriers.

RESULTS

The charge involved in the direct trapping/detrapping mode can be directly assessed with pulsed current-voltage measurements where the time scales and voltages used are consistent with the gate pulse waveforms used in the actual CP measurements [18]. A representative example is shown in fig. 4a. Additionally, a “trap-free” drain current-gate voltage (I_D - V_G) curve, measured fast enough to minimize bulk trapping effects, is required (shown in fig. 4b) [18]. Both types of measurements were performed with a custom built pulsed IV system. Measurement setup details can be found elsewhere [18]. The devices used are $10 \mu\text{m} \times 0.25 \mu\text{m}$ nMOSFETs with dual layer gate stacks consisting of 1 nm SiO_2 interfacial layer, 7 nm HfO_2 , and TiN gate electrodes.

Fig. 4. Representative I_D versus time taken with conditions intended to mimic our CP measurements [18].

As discussed elsewhere [18], for fig. 4a which is consistent with CP between strong inversion/strong accumulation, we calculate an average detrapping current of order 100 pA – 1 nA for a CP frequency of 2 kHz. A range of calculated values

is given due to uncertainties in parameters such as bulk defect location and dielectric constant of the gate stack materials. Further details regarding the calculation procedures and uncertainties are provided in [18].

Fig. 4. “Trap free” I_D - V_G curves [18].

However, we have found experimentally (fig. 5) that the total I_{CP} measured, using the same device and the same strong accumulation/inversion biasing used in fig. 4a, is orders of magnitude smaller (pA levels) than the calculated values [18]. This indicates that most of the detrapped electrons do not contribute to I_{CP} . A possible explanation for the low efficiency of converting detrapping charges into I_{CP} is provided in [18].

Fig. 5: FD-CP for our device when CP between strong inversion and strong accumulation. The measured I_{CP} is orders of magnitude smaller than the average detrapping current calculated from fig. 4 [18].

Fig. 6 illustrates CP results for our device across a relatively wide range of CP frequencies. After converting I_{CP} to charge per cycle, the data shows the commonly observed charge per cycle increase with decreasing CP frequency. As discussed in the introduction, this trend intuitively makes sense. When the CP frequency is lowered, bulk defects further and further away from the interface can start to contribute to the CP process. Establishing the relationship between CP frequency and defect depth will allow for the spatial profiling of the defects.

Given our previous discussions, we now address the question about whether or not this data can be used to extract the bulk defect depth profile. One thing is immediately clear; since we've determined that only a very small fraction of

detrapped charges actually contribute to I_{CP} , (fig. 4) the extracted charge per cycle does not accurately represent the bulk defect density. In other words, even if the frequency to depth relationship can be established, it is *not* a *quantitative* measure of bulk defects.

Fig. 6: I_{CP} versus frequency normalized to charge per cycle. The data shows the commonly observed charge per cycle increase with decreasing CP frequency.

Assume the highest CP frequency contains the least amount of bulk defect contributions. Ideally, at high enough frequency, this will represent a purely interface defect response. All lower frequency measurements will contain this interface defect contribution (normalized to charge per cycle) along with the additional contributions due to bulk defects. We can then subtract the high frequency charge per cycle value from the lower frequency values and determine (very roughly) the charge per cycle due to the fraction of detrapped charges that contribute to I_{CP} . Multiplying the detrapped charge per cycle contribution by CP frequency and converting CP frequency to period, we construct the bulk defect contribution rate vs. period curve of fig 7.

Fig. 7: Extracted bulk defect contribution rate vs. period length (or available time for detrapping/recombination) shows decay behavior similar to fig 4a.

Note that this curve resembles the I_D decay behavior of fig. 4a, suggesting it's tracking the detrapping behavior. (i.e. most of the total detrapping occurs relatively quickly). Can this be

used to determine the bulk defect spatial profile? It's possible, but full of pitfalls. Note that fig. 7 resembles fig. 4a in our case because the minority carrier lifetime is long compared to the period, even at low frequencies. The long minority carrier lifetime ensures a constant recombination rate during each inversion half cycle. Thus, the total recombination is proportional to the total detrapped charges. If this condition is not satisfied, the defect depth to frequency relationship fails. In the other extreme, where the minority carrier lifetime is short for all frequencies (as might be the case for a much lower quality material like SiC) bulk defect profiling is possible since all detrapped charge entering the substrate recombines. If the minority carrier lifetime is somewhere between the extremes, the picture is extremely convoluted. Compounding the situation is the inherent difficulty in actually measuring the minority carrier lifetime, as discussed elsewhere [19, 20].

Another pitfall is that even at the highest CP frequencies, there will always be some detrapping. The detrapping rate rises exponentially with frequency as shown in fig. 7, meaning, our previous assumption about high frequency measurements representing a purely interface defect response is invalid. Quite simply, there is no unique solution to construct fig. 7 accurately. This tends to result in larger defect profile error closer to the interface since the defects closer to the interface are the defects still able to contribute to I_{CP} at higher frequencies.

CONCLUSIONS

Using simple physical arguments, we identified the inherent difficulties associated with defect depth profiling via FD-CP. First, a two-step interface defect mediated tunneling process is unlikely to contribute significantly. Even so, the spatial location of the bulk defect with respect to the interface defect defines the effective tunneling distance which can be very different than the actual distance of the bulk defect away from the interface, resulting in very convoluted depth information. Next, in the direct trapping/detrapping mode, only a small fraction of detrapping charges actually contribute to I_{CP} resulting in a measurement that is not quantitative. Thirdly, the minority carrier lifetime, when compared to the CP period, convolutes the whole picture. Compounding this is the inherent difficulty in accurately measuring minority carrier lifetimes. Finally, even at high frequencies, I_{CP} still contains some contribution from bulk traps. All of these factors contribute to the inherent difficulty of defect depth profiling via FD-CP.

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